

ARTISTIC IMAGERY IN THE STYLE OF THE WRITER

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Annotation

The article analyzes the issues of artistic image and style in modern Uzbek short stories based on Khurshid Dostmuhammad's short story "Yolgiz".

Keywords: artistic work, artistic image, language of artistic work, psychology, author, hero, landscape, portrait.

Artistic imagery is used to increase the vividness and effectiveness of events and emotions in works of art. Artistic image is a very broad concept and defines the important aspects of the style of the work. "The style of a work of art is not only a phenomenon related to its language, but also refers to such elements as image tools, the scope of the work of art expressed through artistic words, the system of images, and compositional construction." From a theoretical point of view, artistic image tools consist of language elements such as alliteration, assonance, archaism, dialectism, slang, inversion, word repetition, syntactic parallelism.

Artistic image serves to provide imagery, which is the primary feature of the language of an artistic work. In this, the ability of the creative imagination of the creator is considered important and determines the writer's own style. All kinds of art such as homonyms, synonyms, antonyms, types of transfer, revitalization, qualification, exaggeration are widely used to increase imagery, i.e., effectiveness. In addition, one of the most important features of increasing the effectiveness of an artistic work is the state of mind, that is, artistic psychology. In works of art, this concept is determined by psychological method. "Psychological analysis can be divided into internal (monologue, memory, associations and images of imagination) and external (expression of emotional uniqueness of facial expressions and other external states of the psyche) forms of character description." Also, characters, monologues and dialogues from artistic speech types are seen as internal types of psychological analysis when revealing the psyche of the hero.

If a person is considered as the main image of a work of art, all other means of representation serve to reveal his psyche. From this point of view, artistic psychologism is one of the most important factors that gathers tools that fully reveal the image of a person and increases the effectiveness of an artistic

work. The character's thoughts, mentality, inner monologue, stream of consciousness, landscape and portrait methods indicate various forms of psychologism.

Usually, writers describe landscapes, i.e. natural scenes based on the mood and state of their characters. The famous Russian writer A. Tolstoy expresses the following opinion about the harmonious expression of the mood of the character and the landscape in fully revealing the psyche of the hero: "Let's say you are describing Ivan Ivanov. He is walking down the street. But you know he's in a bad mood. In this case, how should Ivan Ivanovich be described? You will certainly describe the street scene from the eyes of Ivan Ivanovich, who is walking in a sad state, because he does not see the happy scenes on the street. Although the sun was shining, it seemed misty, cloudy and damp to him."¹.

In our opinion, depicting the real landscape in accordance with the mood of the character, or vice versa, depends more on the style and skill of the writer. To this day, the short story is considered one of the most frequently used epic genres by writers in modern Uzbek literature. As literary types and genres are distinguished in literary studies, the description of psychologism in them is also different. In epic, lyrical and dramatic types, as well as in the genres of the same type, psychological analysis and depiction of the mental state are manifested in a unique way. In particular, the short story genre has wide possibilities for the expression of various psychological methods and artistic speech in illuminating the inner world of the human heart.

In this regard, the scientist M. Bobakhonov, who conducted research on the topic "Psychology in contemporary Uzbek short stories", also emphasizes the short story genre according to the possibilities of the genre for psychological analysis. "However, since describing the inner world of a person - psychologism - is a method of building an image, describing, understanding and evaluating one or another life character, the short story genre can also be a suitable field for such analysis."². Also, the research focused on three different forms of psychologism in fiction. "In literature, the deep artistic study of the human inner world is called "artistic psychologism"³.

In the short stories of Khurshid Dostmuhammad, the landscape is often described based on the hero's mood. We can observe the same landscape

¹ Толстой А.Н. О литературе и искусстве. – М., Сов.писатель, 1956. – Стр 310.

² Бобохонов М. Қиссаларда: Ҳозирги ўзбек қиссачилигида психологизм: Фил. фанлари номзоди...диссертацияси. – Тошкент, 2012. – 31-бет.

³ Бобохонов М. Қиссаларда: Ҳозирги ўзбек қиссачилигида психологизм: Фил. фанлари номзоди...диссертацияси. – Тошкент, 2012.– 18-бет.

described in the following excerpt from Khurshid Dostmuhammad's story "Yolgiz":

"He was pleased when the iron door opened with a familiar light. They pushed, shoved, kicked and insulted the 16-year-old who came in the "Black Beetle" through the door. When he hit it, it would burst his ears - Abdullah saw when he walked three steps that there was a dark shadow inside. "When the moon goes under the clouds, they, that is, owls, chirp and chirp as if enjoying themselves. At this time, there is a sound like moaning from inside the nest of owls..." Abdulla put all his efforts in his ears, he felt that all kinds of insects were whispering and buzzing in the corner of the room, jumping and jumping like grasshoppers. Creeping and squirming, the gnat-like creatures began to close in on the newly arrived aristoans like a body, and began to occupy their bodies with a hungry appetite"⁴.

In the play, in accordance with the depressed mood of Abdulla, who returned from the trial, all his hopes were dashed, and he was alone in the truth, the iron door opened with light, and the moon went behind the clouds, especially the incoherent buzzing of various insects. It was as if his crawling had completely "occupied his organs from inside and outside".

The writer can clearly express the subtle and incomprehensible feelings of the hero's inner experiences in his speech, and in this process skillfully uses various forms of speech: convincingly describes"⁵.

In Khurshid Dostmuhammad's short story "Yolgiz", although Abdulla Qadiri's article is taken as the main event, the author writes his goals and thoughts in his own language. That is, the real events experienced by the hero are combined with the artistic textures of the writer, so that it is difficult for an ordinary reader to notice it. To a certain extent, the formation of this style of the writer was prompted by the skillful use of the "state" of the heroes of Abdulla Qadiri's works, including "The Past Days", "The Feast of the Demons".

Also, the writer considered it his main goal to portray our enlightened intellectuals as persons who had a significant impact on the life of the people: "In the story "Yolgiz", the author shows that not only the works of great artists, but also their personalities are an important support for the spiritual life of people. refers to"⁶. Actually, while analyzing the story, we realize that the place of intellectuals is important in our historical conditions. At the same time, we feel

⁴ Дўстмуҳаммад Х. "Ёлғиз" // Қисса. – Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2021. – 788- б.

⁵ Кўчирма Дўстмуҳаммад Х. Қиссалар. – Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2021. (А.Улуғовнинг кириш сўзидан олинди) – 12- б.

⁶ Кўчирма Дўстмуҳаммад Х. Қиссалар. – Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2021. (А.Улуғовнинг кириш сўзидан олинди) – 22- б.

from their mental state that the intellectuals have become victims of the complexities of the time. That's how the writer's skill can be seen.

If we talk about the short story style, it is necessary to give unique information about the life and creative path of the writer Abdulla Qadiri, the founder of the Uzbek novel, by describing only one event that happened in his life. finding facts and evidences related to biography and artistic and scientific reflection on them constitute the main ideological-aesthetic essence of the story. Abdulla Qadiri, who was appointed as the hero of the story "Yolgiz", has no idea why he was imprisoned, he has been detained for several days without any questioning, and he tortures himself by searching for the reason. He is severely depressed. He will be alone with himself.

The stylistic uniqueness of Khurshid Dostmuhammad is clearly visible in the means of artistic representation, such as portraits, landscapes, mental states.

List of used literature:

1. Бобохонов М. Қиссаларда: Ҳозирги ўзбек қиссачилигида психологизм: Фил. фанлари номзоди...диссертацияси. – Тошкент, 2012.
2. Дўстмуҳаммад Х. Қиссалар. – Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2021.
3. Жирмунский В. Стихотворение Гёте и Байрона: Ты знаешь край? Изд. МГУ, 1961. – 29 стр.
4. Толстой А.Н. О литературе и искусстве. – М., Сов.писатель, 1956.
5. Тулабоева Р. Худойберди Тўхтабоев романларида бадиий психологизм: Филология фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси. – Тошкент, 2019.

